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Student Teacher Relationship Among Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

Affective domain as derived by Blooms in his Taxonomy has taken the center stage in teaching and learning process. Feelings of individual are to be respected while dealing with them in the classroom especially during adolescent stage. In this context teacher's role becomes significant. Teacher has become a facilitator which requires proper rapport with their students. There is a growing understanding that teacher makes a big and deep impact on the life of each and every student which in turn is believed to enhance achievement. Hence the article sheds some light on the influence of Student Teacher relations among Higher Secondary students with some demographic variables like students of differing gender, number of members in the family, order in the family, family income, classroom climate and type of school. It will also highlight the importance of student teacher relationship in modern classroom.

Student Teacher Relationship

Student teacher relationship plays a vital role in the development of an individual as a whole. Many social scientists agree that the same factors which promote psychological development in home will also promote positive behavior in the classroom, which is believed to facilitate learning and achievement as school has become the second home to the adolescent child. Class teacher's enormous authority has been an outdated phenomenon. Teachers' role has changed from a task master in Gurukula system to facilitator in the classroom. A corporal punishment in school is an expired concept. Records flying and students trembling at the sight of teachers are history. Unfortunately, teacher the embodiment of truth and knowledge is also a huge question. In today's classroom, adolescent student is treated as a customer, who has to be advised, guided, counseled and treated well by giving individual attention to gain significant academic performance. He/she is open, expressive, and bold with ideas, updated with current information and tech savvy who hates authority and advice. In this changing times, student teacher relations gains significance in terms of contribution to academic achievement. The academic relation between the teacher and the student is known as teacher student relationship. In modern classrooms, relationship between teacher and adolescent child involves building coalitions, among multiple contrasting groups; interact in a way that enriches each other guided by the principle of mutual trust.

Why to have Better Student Teacher Relations

When students believe that teacher is a source of knowledge and symbol of trust to look forward to, adolescent student will respect and obey the words of the teacher. A positive relationship between the two

will change the teaching learning process a joyful and meaningful experience to both the teacher and student provided without compromising on the teaching learning activities. Researchers have found that teachers' attitude influence students' attitude (**Aiken, 1970**). Furthermore teacher can be a real source of inspiration if he/she is able to generate value among the students for what is taught. Moreover, when the teacher is multi-task oriented and interacts with the students without any feeling of status, power or authority, he/she will likely to have more followers among the adolescent student community. Further a teacher should act his emotions but never show real emotions to control and discipline the students and maintain a balance between discipline, sympathy and empathy. Teacher should further respect the dignity and respect of the students to gain respect and trust and should give recognition for all the good that the student has done. All these factors will contribute positively to student teacher relations.

Some Factors to Facilitate Positive Student Teacher Relations

In today's classrooms, especially adolescents' should be allowed to students to express their feelings within the accepted norms and standards of the society.

- Never show partiality and always stand for the right cause as this will win trust on the teacher.
- Provide necessary guidance, support and needed information to students where ever necessary in all possible aspects.
- Maintain discipline judiciously.
- Never lose temper with the students while punishing.
- Maintain democratic style of functioning when dealing with students.
- Teach the concepts in simple and interesting way.
- Participate with students in organizing co-curricular, extra-curricular activities.

Student Teacher Relations with Academic Achievement

Gone are the days where, teachers are considered as symbol of authority demanding unquestionable obedience. In today's world teachers are perceived as friends, fellow companion and partners in school with a mission of providing opportunities for the adolescents to explore. This relationship translates itself into better performance in school.

STUDIES ON STUDENT TEACHER RELATION WITH SOME DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS

Student Teacher relations with Gender

Studies show that Student Teacher Relations between adolescent boys and girls, as such doesn't have any major difference. This is because the expectations of students about a teacher are more or less the same for

boys and girls. Students expect teachers to be more democratic in their approach, show greater levels of understanding and respect individual dignity. Both have similar levels of student teacher relations.

Student Teacher relations with Number of Members in the family

Studies reveal that number of members in a family doesn't have any significant influence on Student Teacher Relations among adolescents. Though studies show that larger is the family greater is the social development, resulting in developing mature relationships. The subject under study is basically nuclear families and hence, no significant difference is seen between number of family members is three and number of family members is four with respect to students relation with the teacher.

Furthermore, Birth order in the family really matters when family members or teachers have different expectations. In this case, teachers have similar expectations on the child irrespective of the birth order.

Student Teacher relations with family Income

Studies reveal that adolescents from higher and lower income families, have not much difference, in their level of student teacher relations as there is no major discrimination in schools by teachers, based on students' family standards and income.

Student Teacher Relations with Type of School

Studies show that student teacher relations among adolescents in government, aided and matriculation schools are similar. Primary motive is, students come to learn and a teacher, to teach and in the process better understanding is developed. Teachers have become more of friends than a person of authority. Adolescents are given freedom with boundaries drawn clearly as to what is expected of them. A teacher inside the class is perceived as disciplined person expecting obedience from students as he has been given the responsibility of guiding the students while, outside the classroom, he is an ordinary person. This style of functioning by teachers is common in all types of schools and is well received by the student community. This might have been the added reason for Student Teacher Relations among different type of schools to be similar

Student Teacher relations with Classroom Climate

The class size, organization, teaching, teacher student relation, peer relation and disciplinary philosophy, all contributes to the overall climate of the classroom; this climate, more than any other factor, influences student teacher relations especially during adolescents. Most central to positive perceptions of class, is the extent of students' involvement. Researchers found that students' grades were most satisfied and successful when the learning environment was relaxed. So, better classroom environment will add to positive student teacher relations.

Conclusion

In today's world student teacher relations with adolescents increases positively as students move higher grades. Teachers are capable of encouraging, motivating, channelizing the students' energy towards reaching the goal. Teachers and students have realized the need for fostering better understanding among themselves in this changed scenario of individual dignity, respect and freedom. By having a better understanding, with teachers, students realize their duties voluntarily, without much force of compulsion. So teachers should change the approach in the classroom by being concerned, building rapport, and inspire students to have meaningful academic achievement. Good student teacher relations will go a long way in building a better classroom environment which will have a positive bearing on their academic achievement.

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A STUDY ON STUDENT TEACHER RELATIONSHIP AMONG ADOLESCENTS

T Arun Christopher, Research Scholar, SCSVMV University &
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